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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE
OF GENERAL POPULATION TOWARDS EPISTAXIS IN
SAUDI ARABIA**

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Abstract

Introduction: epistaxis is acute bleeding from the nasopharynx or the nose. Epistaxis is a common problem and it ranges from mild to severe bleeding, also it considers as life-threatening rhinological emergency.

Objective: To evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practice towards epistaxis in Saudi population.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study based on questionnaire distributed randomly on 600 Saudi participants in the period from November to December 2018. The data was collected using excel sheet and analysis was performed by using SPSS.

Results: 600 Saudi participants filled the questionnaires, the vast majority of participants 200(33.3%) were between 20 -30 years old. About half of the patients were female and other half males. 110 participants (18.3) had epistaxis, the vast majority don't know either chronic diseases or medication are risk factors for epistaxis (82%) and (74%) respectively. Almost two-third of participants believe that dealing with nose and environmental factors are risk factors for epistaxis (66% and 68%) respectively. Regarding stopping bleeding (77.7%) said compression on the nose will stop bleeding.

Conclusion: knowledge of participants about epistaxis management was acceptable among Saudi populations. We suggest filling the gap to increase the public campaigns to increase the level of awareness among general population.

Keywords: Epistaxis, Population, Saudi, Kap.

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INTRODUCTION:

Epistaxis is defined as the acute bleeding from the nasal cavity, nasopharynx or the nose [1]. The majority of bleeding from the nasal septum [2]. Epistaxis is a common otorhinolaryngology emergency in ear, nose, and throat (ENT) [3]. It acts as a significant workload in accident and emergency. Also, it usually causes anxiety for both patients and physicians [1]. Severity from mild bleeding to severe, life-threatening rhinological emergency which acts as a challenge to doctors [4]. The nasal bleeding caused by either systemic or local causes, the systemic factors involved blood disorders, the use of anticoagulant and arterial high blood pressure, while the local factors included upper airway infections, nasal allergies, the introduction of foreign bodies into the nasal cavity and trauma [5]. The incidence of epistaxis was reported to range from 10% to 60 % of individuals [6]. One study revealed 6% of individuals were admitted to medical treatment to control the hemorrhage, while 60% of them had at least one episode of epistaxis throughout their lifetime and it was mentioned that males were more prone to experience epistaxis than females [7]. Epistaxis is common among young adults and children, while it is rare among neonates, in the sixth decade it reaches its peak [8]. First aid is important to reduce mortality and morbidity of the emergency case especially in persistent bleeding cases [10]. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practice towards epistaxis in the general Saudi population.

METHODS:**Study design**

This study included 600 Saudi participants; the study was conducted in the period from November to December 2018. This study was performed using questionnaire to assess demographics, knowledge,

attitude, and practice of participants. Questionnaires were distributed randomly among participants.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS.

RESULTS:

The present study included 600 Saudi participants. The vast majority of participants 200(33.3%) were between 20 -30 years old, 171 (28.5%) were in the age range of 31-40 years old, 146 (24.3%) in the age range 41-50 years and those between 51-60 were only 83(18.3%). The females were more than males 322(53.7%) and 278 (46.3%) respectively. Regarding marital status, there were 438 (73%) married, 162 (27%) single. 110 (18.3) had epistaxis, and 490 (81.7) didn't have it. Most of the participants had college degree 340 (56.7%), followed by those with school degree 234 (39%) and only 26 (4.3%) were illiterate. (Table 1).

Regarding KAP, the vast majority don't know either chronic diseases or medication are risk factors for epistaxis (82%) and (74%) respectively. Almost two-third of participants believe that dealing with nose and environmental factors are risk factors for epistaxis (66% and 68%) respectively. Regarding stopping bleeding (77.7%) said compression on the nose will stop bleeding, also (53%) believe that laying on backward is the optimal position to stop bleeding. When we come to practice, we found that (53.3%) compromised on cartilage of the nose to stop bleeding while (46.7%) compromised on the bony part of the nose to stop bleeding. In addition, more than (90%) of participants will go to hospital if bleeding didn't stop. Regarding the attitude, (73.3%) do not know who is managing the epistaxis while (26.7%) chose by ENT doctors. (Table 2).

Table1: demographic information of participants:

Demographics (N)		Number/Percentage
Age	20-30	200 (33.3%)
	31-40	171 (28.5%)
	41-50	146 (24.3%)
	51-60	83 (13.8%)
Sex	Females	322 (53.7%)
	Males	278 (46.3%)
Marital status	Single	162 (27%)
	Married	438 (73%)
Having epistaxis	Yes	110 (18.3%)
	No	490 (81.7%)
Education level	Illiterate	26 (4.3%)
	School degree	234 (39%)
	College degree	340 (56.7%)

Table2: knowledge, practice, and attitude of participants about epistaxis

Questions	Answers	N	%
Knowledge			
Chronic diseases are a risk factor	Yes	42	7
	No	64	10.7
	Don't know	494	82.3
Some medicinal is risk factors	Yes	68	11.3
	No	88	14.7
	Don't know	444	74
Dealing with nose is a risk factor	Yes	397	66.2
	No	106	17.7
	Don't know	97	16.1
Environmental factors may be a cause	Yes	409	68.2
	No	102	17
	Don't know	89	14.8
Compressing nose is beneficial to stop bleeding	Yes	466	77.7
	No	54	9
	Don't know	80	13.3
Optimal position to stop bleeding	Leaning head forward	169	28.2
	Backwards	322	53.7
	Abdomen	8	1.3
	Back	101	16.8
Practice			
Which part comprised	Bony	280	46.7
	Cartilage	320	53.3

Mechanism of breathing during epistaxis	By mouth up to epistaxis stop	350	58.3
	By nose	80	13.3
	Don't know	170	28.3
What is should be done if bleeding doesn't stop	Refer to hospital	545	90.8
	Waiting up to bleeding stop	55	9.2
Attitudes			
Who perform management	I don't know	440	73.3
	ENT doctor	160	26.7

DISCUSSION:

Our study was aimed to assess KAP of general Saudi population toward epistaxis. The current study included 600 participants. The large majority of participants were adults.

whereas the least percent of participants had age between 51-60 years. Females were more than males in this study and the large majority of participants were married. More than half of participants have college degree. There were questions to investigate the knowledge, practice and attitude Participants were asked if the chronic disease was a risk factor, most of the participants 82.3% didn't know.

Also, the majority of participants (74%) didn't know if some medicinal were risk factors or not. There were 66.2% thought that dealing with nose was a risk factor and 68.2% thought that environmental factors cause of epistaxis. High percent 77.7% thought that compressing nose was beneficial to stop bleeding and the optimal position to stop bleeding was leaning head backward (53.7%). In the practice part, 53.3% said that cartilage was the part comprised to stop epistaxis, 90.8% of individuals said that referring to the hospital is the solution to stop bleeding if the bleeding didn't stop. In the attitude part: 73.3% do not know that whom manage epistaxis.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, we found that knowledge towards epistaxis was acceptable among Saudi populations. We suggest to fill the gap to increase the public campaigns to increase the level of awareness among general population.

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